

NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PROCESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the educational and didactic possibilities of modern pedagogical technologies, the use of which is one of the prospective directions of the development of higher education. The writer presents the algorithm and processually powerful acknowledgment of educational advances, which are most effectively utilized in the proficient planning of students, specifically: portfolio technology, project technology, technology of improvement of thinking and writing.

Advanced education alongside certain pointers describing creative capability of a nation is one of the variables of marketability of Uzbekistan economy. The presentation of technological advancements in the educational course of higher school can help to choose the undertakings of arrangement of experts lined up with the time. The assignment of present day higher school is an expansion of capability of teachers in the space of profoundly powerful utilization of data, correspondence and interactive technologies, creation and improvement of widespread pedagogical circle, incitement of development of the new culture of pedagogical thinking.

The utilization of present day pedagogical technologies in the pedagogical interaction of an organization of advanced education makes very new potential outcomes of

acknowledgment of pedagogical standards of individualization and separation of guidance, impacts decidedly on the turn of events of intellectual movement of students, their inventive action, awareness, understands the terms of progress from instructing to self-training.

The effectiveness of the utilization of pedagogical advancements in pedagogical cycle is affirmed by research works of number of creators: G. K. Selevko, V. I. Andreev, V. P. Bepal'ko, V. I. Bogoljubov, M. V. Klarin, V. J. Pitjukov, V. A. Slastjonin, J. A. Savel'ev and others. These days careful hypothetical turn of events of the issue of use of present day pedagogical advances in the proficient arrangement of an expert in the provisions of higher school obtains exceptional significance and importance.

Current advancements in instruction are seen as means by dint of which another

pedagogical worldview can be figured it out. The most broad translation of the idea "technology " comprises in the way that it addresses deductively and for all intents and purposes grounded arrangement of action, which is applied by a person with the end goal of change of the climate, creation of material or profound qualities. V. P. Besimal'ko noticed that any action can be either an technology or a craftsmanship. A workmanship depends on instinct, an technology – on science. Everything starts with a craftsmanship, and finishes with an technology to start again.

Any arranging, without which in you can't do the pedagogical action, clashes with an offhand, acting by instinct, and in this way can be considered as the start of technology .

In the academic science and practice one can uncover the presence of different translations of pedagogical technology . What's more, it isn't easygoing, as each creator comes up to comprehension of the quintessence of technology in everyday procedure from the certain reasonable methodology.

Anyway all existent positions are described by the following focuses:

an technology is intentionally produced for the certain academic expectation, in its premise there is a methodological, philosophical situation of the creator;

an innovative chain of activities and tasks is masterminded rigorously as per targets, which have a structure of a substantial anticipated outcome;

working of an technology conceives the interrelated movement of an educator with students on a legally binding premise

taking into account standards of individualization and separation, ideal acknowledgment of human and specialized potential outcomes, use of discourse and correspondence;

the stage-by-stage arranging and progressive exemplification of the components of an pedagogical technology should be, from one side, imitated by any educator and, from the other, ensure the accomplishment of the arranged outcomes by all students ;

the natural piece of any pedagogical technology comprises in analytic techniques, containing the standards, files and instruments of estimation of the after effects of action.

The purpose of the article. While giving students proficient preparing distinctive creative advances are utilized. In this article we will harp on some of them, in particular: Portfolio Technology; Task Technology; Technology of Development of Critical Thinking what's more, Writing.

Simultaneously an unavoidable piece of any concentrated on course, through which current pedagogical technology s are figured it out by and by, is an orderly intricate which, as we would see it, should include:

video PC framework, through which an instructor conducts talks and classes in the uncommonly prepared address rooms;

"screen shot", some exceptional hand-out, the particular of which is that other than a correspondence data work, it achieves an element of the activizer of the inventive movement of an understudy in the interaction of filling by him of uncommonly planned graphs, boxes, registries, etc;

a bunch of interactive specialized and program preparing assets.

Allow us to think about a calculation and processually successful acknowledgment of each of prior assigned advancements. Generally not set in stone as an assortment of works furthermore, aftereffects of a student, which shows his/her endeavors, progress and accomplishments in various regions. This technology supplements the conventional controlling and assessing offices which are coordinated, when in doubt, towards the check of the conceptive degree of dominating of data, truth based and algorithmic information and capacities. Portfolio technology permits considering the outcomes, achieved by an understudy in the different sorts of movement – pedagogical , innovative, melodic and performing, informative and others and is the significant component of the action way to deal with schooling.

Portfolio isn't just the advanced powerful type of assessment yet additionally assists with choosing significant pedagogical assignments: to help high pedagogical inspiration of students ; to support their action furthermore, independence, to expand potential outcomes of learning and selflearning; to foster abilities of reflexive and evaluative movement of future trained professionals. The portrayed provisions of portfolio make out of it the promising type of show of the singular direction of pedagogical accomplishments of a distinct understudy, which replies the assignments of his/her expert planning. The Introduction of portfolio technology made it conceivable to expand the pedagogical action of the students of the Department of Foreign Languages, the level of their

acknowledgment of own points and potential outcomes.

While fostering the portfolio we center around its three sorts:

1. "Expertly orderly portfolio", which incorporates: material for the examples (pedagogical); game and engaging material (games, tests, cross-words, engaging errands); educational material (plans of examples, learning helps, edifices of errands); material for extracurricular work (situations of occasions, nights, subjects of conversations, etc); a sound library for acknowledgment of extracurricular exercises. A particularly model infers the chance of both subjective and quantitative assessment of the materials of portfolio. "Expertly systematic portfolio" will be helpful for the students during their school practice and their further proficient action.
2. "Arrangement of works" is an assortment of various imaginative, project what's more, research works, and furthermore the portrayal of fundamental structures and bearings of its pedagogical and innovative action: interest in meetings, contests, extra courses, and so forth This variation of portfolio infers subjective assessment, for instance, as per the boundaries of assortment and influence of materials, nature of the introduced works, direction to the picked subject matter. Portfolio is orchestrated in a structure of an understudy's innovative organizer with the connection of his/her works, introduced as texts, electronic forms, photographs, video records. Arrangement of this kind gives a wide thought regarding the elements of pedagogical and innovative action of an understudy, character of expert direction.

Here we offer the commendable variation of records in the "arrangement of works":

projects (the subject of the undertaking and the depiction of work are given, there can likewise be a connection in the structure of photographs, text of work (printed or electronic form), and so forth);

research works and reports (concentrated on materials, names of work, delineations and other are determined);

imaginative works (the rundown of works is given);

support in rivalries, celebrations, challenges (the subject, timing and accomplished outcomes are determined);

interest in logical viable and hypothetical gatherings, classes, and so forth (the topic of occasion, the name of the association, which leads the occasion, the type of understudy's support in it and result are determined);

different types of imaginative action (investment in interest gatherings furthermore, different circles and social orders). Managing the "arrangement of works": students can likewise all things considered voluntarily, or on their instructor's guidelines, select for their "dossier" different sorts of composed works done in this teach.

3. "Arrangement of surveys" incorporates attributes of understudy's mentality to various sorts of movement, and furthermore understudy's own writing investigation of his/her positive movement and its outcomes. Portfolio can be introduced as texts-ends, audits, remarks, resumes, papers, reference and bless your heart letter (for instance, after a time of showing practice) and so on. This type of

portfolio offers a chance to actuate the systems of students' self-assessment, which advances the level of acknowledgment of the cycles identified with instruction. Here is the model rundown of records in the "arrangement of surveys": an end with respect to the nature of the executed work; surveys of the articles, reports, research works; references about the work in an inventive group, appearances at gatherings, rivalries or challenges; a resume ready by an understudy with the assessment of own pedagogical accomplishments.

The reason for project technology is the turn of events of intellectual interests of students, capacities to build information autonomously, capacities to orientate in the enlightening space,

the advancement of thinking. Undertaking technology consistently centers on the autonomous movement of students (individual, pair, bunch), which is finished by students during the specific range of time. The essential necessities to the utilization of task technology are event of an issue or an assignment which is huge in research and innovative terms and require incorporated information and analytical look for its answer; pragmatic, hypothetical, and intellectual importance of the alleged outcomes; free (individual, pair, bunch) movement of students; organizing of the meaningful piece of a task (with sign of stage-by-stage results); utilization of examination strategies (assurance of an issue and errands of an exploration which follow from it and shaping of the theory of their tackling; conversation of examination techniques; drawing up of inevitable outcomes; investigation of the acquired information; summing up, refreshing, ends).

We have characterized the rules for the evaluation of the improvement of a venture. To these rules we allude the importance what's more, topicality of the issues which have been raised; the fundamental and adequate profundity of entrance into an issue and the inclusion of information from various regions for its choice; culmination, meaningfulness of an undertaking; topicality and potential of an undertaking. It is important to construct training on dynamic premise, through sensible movement of an understudy, agreeing with his/her own interest precisely in this information. Consequently it is critical to show students their very own advantage in the procured information which can and should be helpful for them in their further proficient movement. In this association it is important to pick an issue which is critical for a future trained professional. It must be an issue for the arrangement of which he needs to apply information which has been as of now acquired and during the method involved with settling of which to get new information. Herewith, the errand of an educator to recommend new channels of data or simply steer understudy musings the correct way for a free inquiry. The selection of subjects of activities is characterized by an educator with due respect to the pedagogical circumstance on the discipline which is under study, or by students themselves, if the project is planned for extracurricular action. The work on a task generally comprises of a couple of stages:

1. The looking through stage (assurance of targets of a task, acknowledgment of hierarchical work; definition of an issue of an examination; assurance of an article and a subject of an examination; guessing).

2. The planning stage (assurance of headings of work and quick errands; assurance of strategies for search of channels of data by headings; assurance of research techniques; association of gatherings; gathering of undertakings).

3. The innovative stage (free work in gatherings, trade of data; execution of the set up innovative tasks; quality checking; investigation of the data gathered by gatherings, working out of the situation of the safeguard of a task which is organized in the accompanying way: meaning of a task; guard of the theory; ends, clarification as tables, diagrams, pictures etc; replies to questions.

4. The last stage (board conversation, assessment of a venture, examination of the consequences of execution of an undertaking; ends). Subsequently students need to take care of an issue freely and by joint endeavors, applying fundamental information here and there from various regions, and get a genuine and recognizable outcome. The aftereffects of the executed activities should be material, for example appropriately planned (a collection, a report, a paper, and so on) Thus, the advancement of intellectual abilities of students, the capacities to frame their own insight autonomously also, orientate oneself in useful space, the advancement of the basic speculation lie at the base of undertaking technology. Critical thinking is the capacity to bring up new issues, elaborate different contentions and settle on autonomous conscious choices.

The advancement of this sort of thinking through the interactive inclusion of students into the pedagogical interaction is

the point of the other technology under assessment.

Technology of advancement of critical thinking and writing has its own specific elements, in particular: accentuation on the autonomy of students in the pedagogical cycle; search of the contentions for the arrangement of an issue; capacity not to accept the data based on previous experience with no check; search of sensible replies, which is the aftereffect of reflection and disclosure of the obscure; plan of conditions for coordinated effort and association simultaneously of deliberate action. The technology comprises of a couple of stages, in particular: 1 actuation (of the material on the theme which students definitely know); appreciation (of the gained data); 2 reflection (determination of data).

Every one of the prior periods of the technology of improvement of thinking incorporates essential strategies:

stage 1: a bunch, a person "conceptualizing", a gathering "conceptualizing";

stage 2: an addition (increasing of data, increasing of a text), perusing with stops, befuddle conversation, course of action of information in a consistent request (I know, I need to know, I have to know) the point of which is systematization of information on the point; 3

stage 3: a group ("pedagogical bunch", strategy for realistic systematization of material), an article, a cinquain (a sonnet of five lines, the point of which is to

orchestrate and sum up data on the point). Reflection is a fast strategy of summarization on the point, technique for summarizing of the gotten data and giving a record of troublesome thoughts, sentiments and ideas in a couple of words.

Technology of advancement of thinking is the establishment for dominating of new sorts of action. The subject of any new pedagogical technology is substantial co-tasks of students and instructors in various kinds of movement, which are coordinated on the base of exact organizing, systematization, programming, algorithmization, normalization of strategies and procedures of instructing or teaching, with presentation of computerization and procedure offices.

Conclusion: Thus, current academic technology s understand the prospectus and give the accomplishment of the set pedagogical destinations recently, suggesting the logical ways to deal with the association of pedagogical interaction in the foundation of higher learning. They expand the scope of pedagogical administrations presented to students , change and give new structures, strategies and method for instruction. Utilization of current pedagogical technology s is quite possibly the most encouraging direction of the development of higher education, which promote more profound individualization and intensification of educational process, shaping and self-actualization of the personality of a future specialist.

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